

Particle emission from pulsars: bibliography

Silvia Manconi^{1,*}

¹*Laboratoire d'Annecy-le-Vieux de Physique Théorique (LAPTh), CNRS, USMB, F-74940 Annecy, France*

(Dated: May 30, 2023)

In this document we collect a bibliography for the talk given at 3rd EuCAPT symposium with the title: "Particle emission from pulsars" on 31/5/23, to facilitate the exploration of the topic to anyone interested. Please apologize my non-complete selection: if you believe an important piece of work or review is missing, please reach me at manconi@lapth.cnrs.fr.

-
- [1] J. K. Daugherty and A. K. Harding, Electromagnetic cascades in pulsars., *Astrophys. J.* **252**, 337 (1982).
 - [2] F. A. Aharonian, S. V. Bogovalov, and D. Khangulyan, Abrupt acceleration of a 'cold' ultrarelativistic wind from the Crab pulsar, *Nature* **482N7386**, 507 (2012).
 - [3] I. A. Grenier and A. K. Harding, Gamma-ray pulsars: a gold mine, *Comptes Rendus Physique* **16**, 641 (2015), [arXiv:1509.08823 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1509.08823).
 - [4] A. K. Harding, C. Venter, and C. Kalapotharakos, Very-high-energy Emission from Pulsars, *Astrophys. J.* **923**, 194 (2021), [arXiv:2110.09412 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.09412).
 - [5] G. Giacinti, A. M. W. Mitchell, R. López-Coto, V. Joshi, R. D. Parsons, and J. A. Hinton, Halo fraction in TeV-bright pulsar wind nebulae, *Astron. Astrophys.* **636**, A113 (2020), [arXiv:1907.12121 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1907.12121).
 - [6] O. Porth, S. S. Komissarov, and R. Keppens, Three-Dimensional Magnetohydrodynamic Simulations of the Crab Nebula, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **438**, 278 (2014), [arXiv:1310.2531 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1310.2531).
 - [7] C. Guépin, B. Cerutti, and K. Kotera, Proton acceleration in pulsar magnetospheres, *Astron. Astrophys.* **635**, A138 (2020), [arXiv:1910.11387 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.11387).
 - [8] A. M. W. Mitchell and J. Gelfand, Pulsar Wind Nebulae [10.1007/978-981-16-4544-0_157](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.1007/978-981-16-4544-0_157) – 1 (2022), [arXiv:2208.11026 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2208.11026).
 - [9] B. Olmi and N. Bucciantini, From young to old: the evolutionary path of Pulsar Wind Nebulae [10.1017/pasa.2023.5](https://arxiv.org/abs/10.1017/pasa.2023.5) (2023), [arXiv:2301.12903 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.12903).
 - [10] M. Di Mauro, S. Manconi, and F. Donato, Detection of a γ -ray halo around Geminga with the Fermi -LAT data and implications for the positron flux, *Phys. Rev. D* **100**, 123015 (2019), [Erratum: *Phys.Rev.D* 104, 089903 (2021)], [arXiv:1903.05647 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.05647).
 - [11] F. Aharonian *et al.* (H.E.S.S.), Detection of extended gamma-ray emission around the Geminga pulsar with H.E.S.S., *Astron. Astrophys.* **673**, A148 (2023), [arXiv:2304.02631 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2304.02631).
 - [12] A. U. Abeysekara *et al.* (HAWC), Extended gamma-ray sources around pulsars constrain the origin of the positron flux at Earth, *Science* **358**, 911 (2017), [arXiv:1711.06223 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.06223).
 - [13] Y. Guo, Y. Zhang, Q. Yuan, and H. Hu (LHAASO), Observations of extended very-high-energy halos around Geminga and Monogem with the LHAASO-KM2A, *PoS ICRC2021*, 852 (2021).
 - [14] K. Fang, Gamma-ray pulsar halos in the Galaxy, *Front. Astron. Space Sci.* **9**, 1022100 (2022), [arXiv:2209.13294 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.13294).
 - [15] R.-Y. Liu, The physics of pulsar halos: Research progress and prospect, *Int. J. Mod. Phys. A* **37**, 2230011 (2022), [arXiv:2207.04011 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2207.04011).
 - [16] R. López-Coto, E. de Oña Wilhelmi, F. Aharonian, E. Amato, and J. Hinton, Gamma-ray haloes around pulsars as the key to understanding cosmic-ray transport in the Galaxy, *Nature Astron.* **6**, 199 (2022), [arXiv:2202.06899 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2202.06899).
 - [17] X. Tang and T. Piran, Positron flux and γ -ray emission from Geminga pulsar and pulsar wind nebula, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **484**, 3491 (2019), [arXiv:1808.02445 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.02445).
 - [18] G. Johannesson, T. A. Porter, and I. V. Moskalenko, Cosmic-Ray Propagation in Light of the Recent Observation of Geminga, *Astrophys. J.* **879**, 91 (2019), [arXiv:1903.05509 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.05509).
 - [19] H. Jacobs, P. Mertsch, and V. H. M. Phan, Unstable cosmic-ray nuclei constrain low-diffusion zones in the Galactic disk, (2023), [arXiv:2305.10337 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2305.10337).
 - [20] S. Recchia, M. Di Mauro, F. A. Aharonian, L. Orusa, F. Donato, S. Gabici, and S. Manconi, Do the Geminga, Monogem and PSR J0622+3749 γ -ray halos imply slow diffusion around pulsars?, *Phys. Rev. D* **104**, 123017 (2021), [arXiv:2106.02275 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/2106.02275).
 - [21] R.-Y. Liu, H. Yan, and H. Zhang, Understanding the Multiwavelength Observation of Geminga's Tev Halo: The Role of Anisotropic Diffusion of Particles, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **123**, 221103 (2019), [arXiv:1904.11536 \[astro-ph.HE\]](https://arxiv.org/abs/1904.11536).

* manconi@lapth.cnrs.fr

- [22] P. De La Torre Luque, O. Fornieri, and T. Linden, Anisotropic diffusion cannot explain TeV halo observations, *Phys. Rev. D* **106**, 123033 (2022), [arXiv:2205.08544 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [23] M. Di Mauro, S. Manconi, and F. Donato, Evidences of low-diffusion bubbles around Galactic pulsars, *Phys. Rev. D* **101**, 103035 (2020), [arXiv:1908.03216 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [24] M. Di Mauro, S. Manconi, M. Negro, and F. Donato, Investigating γ -ray halos around three HAWC bright sources in Fermi-LAT data, *Phys. Rev. D* **104**, 103002 (2021), [arXiv:2012.05932 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [25] T. Sudoh, T. Linden, and J. F. Beacom, TeV Halos are Everywhere: Prospects for New Discoveries, *Phys. Rev. D* **100**, 043016 (2019), [arXiv:1902.08203 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [26] C. Eckner, V. Vodeb, P. Martin, G. Zaharijas, and F. Calore, Detecting and characterizing pulsar haloes with the Cherenkov telescope array, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **521**, 3793 (2023), [arXiv:2212.11265 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [27] P. Martin, A. Marcowith, and L. Tibaldo, Are pulsar halos rare? - Modeling the halos around PSRs J0633+1746 and B0656+14 in the light of Fermi-LAT, HAWC, and AMS-02 observations and extrapolating to other nearby pulsars, *Astron. Astrophys.* **665**, A132 (2022), [arXiv:2206.11803 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [28] B. Li, Y. Zhang, T. Liu, R.-Y. Liu, and X.-Y. Wang, Prospect of detecting X-ray haloes around middle-aged pulsars with eROSITA, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **513**, 2884 (2022), [arXiv:2110.08856 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [29] M. Aguilar, L. Ali Cavazonza, G. Ambrosi, *et al.* (AMS Collaboration), Towards understanding the origin of cosmic-ray positrons, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **122**, 041102 (2019).
- [30] M. Di Mauro, F. Donato, M. Korsmeier, S. Manconi, and L. Orusa, A novel prediction for secondary positrons and electrons in the Galaxy, (2023), [arXiv:2304.01261 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [31] S. Manconi, M. Di Mauro, and F. Donato, Contribution of pulsars to cosmic-ray positrons in light of recent observation of inverse-Compton halos, *Phys. Rev. D* **102**, 023015 (2020), [arXiv:2001.09985 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [32] L. Orusa, S. Manconi, F. Donato, and M. Di Mauro, Constraining positron emission from pulsar populations with AMS-02 data, *JCAP* **12** (12), 014, [arXiv:2107.06300 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [33] C. Evoli, E. Amato, P. Blasi, and R. Aloisio, Galactic factories of cosmic-ray electrons and positrons, *Phys. Rev. D* **103**, 083010 (2021), [arXiv:2010.11955 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [34] K. Asano, Y. Asaoka, Y. Akaike, N. Kawanaka, K. Kohri, H. M. Motz, and T. Terasawa, Monte Carlo Study of Electron and Positron Cosmic-Ray Propagation with the CALET Spectrum, *Astrophys. J.* **926**, 5 (2022), [arXiv:2111.09636 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [35] I. Cholis and I. Krommydas, Utilizing cosmic-ray positron and electron observations to probe the averaged properties of Milky Way pulsars, *Phys. Rev. D* **105**, 023015 (2022), [arXiv:2111.05864 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [36] S. Manconi, M. Di Mauro, and F. Donato, Dipole anisotropy in cosmic electrons and positrons: inspection on local sources, *JCAP* **01**, 006, [arXiv:1611.06237 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [37] I. Krommydas and I. Cholis, Revisiting GeV-scale annihilating dark matter with the AMS-02 positron fraction, *Phys. Rev. D* **107**, 023003 (2023), [arXiv:2210.04903 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [38] S. Murgia, The Fermi-LAT Galactic Center Excess: Evidence of Annihilating Dark Matter?, *Ann. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci.* **70**, 455 (2020).
- [39] R. Bartels, E. Storm, C. Weniger, and F. Calore, The Fermi-LAT GeV excess as a tracer of stellar mass in the Galactic bulge, *Nature Astron.* **2**, 819 (2018), [arXiv:1711.04778 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [40] O. Macias, C. Gordon, R. M. Crocker, B. Coleman, D. Paterson, S. Horiuchi, and M. Pohl, Galactic bulge preferred over dark matter for the Galactic centre gamma-ray excess, *Nature Astron.* **2**, 387 (2018), [arXiv:1611.06644 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [41] F. Calore, F. Donato, and S. Manconi, Dissecting the Inner Galaxy with γ -Ray Pixel Count Statistics, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **127**, 161102 (2021), [arXiv:2102.12497 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [42] M. Di Mauro, Characteristics of the Galactic Center excess measured with 11 years of *Fermi*-LAT data, *Phys. Rev. D* **103**, 063029 (2021), [arXiv:2101.04694 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [43] S. D. McDermott, Y.-M. Zhong, and I. Cholis, A Phantom Menace: On the Morphology of the Galactic Center Excess, (2022), [arXiv:2209.00006 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [44] I. Cholis, Y.-M. Zhong, S. D. McDermott, and J. P. Surdutovich, Return of the templates: Revisiting the Galactic Center excess with multimessenger observations, *Phys. Rev. D* **105**, 103023 (2022), [arXiv:2112.09706 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [45] M. Pohl, O. Macias, P. Coleman, and C. Gordon, Assessing the Impact of Hydrogen Absorption on the Characteristics of the Galactic Center Excess, *Astrophys. J.* **929**, 136 (2022), [arXiv:2203.11626 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [46] F. List, N. L. Rodd, and G. F. Lewis, Extracting the Galactic Center excess' source-count distribution with neural nets, *Phys. Rev. D* **104**, 123022 (2021), [arXiv:2107.09070 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [47] S. Mishra-Sharma and K. Cranmer, Neural simulation-based inference approach for characterizing the Galactic Center γ -ray excess, *Phys. Rev. D* **105**, 063017 (2022), [arXiv:2110.06931 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [48] J. Petrović, P. D. Serpico, and G. Zaharijas, Millisecond pulsars and the Galactic Center gamma-ray excess: the importance of luminosity function and secondary emission, *JCAP* **02**, 023, [arXiv:1411.2980 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [49] T. Linden, N. L. Rodd, B. R. Safdi, and T. R. Slatyer, High-energy tail of the Galactic Center gamma-ray excess, *Phys. Rev. D* **94**, 103013 (2016), [arXiv:1604.01026 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [50] O. Macias, H. van Leijen, D. Song, S. Ando, S. Horiuchi, and R. M. Crocker, Cherenkov Telescope Array sensitivity to the putative millisecond pulsar population responsible for the Galactic Centre excess, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **506**, 1741 (2021), [arXiv:2102.05648 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [51] D. Song, O. Macias, S. Horiuchi, R. M. Crocker, and D. M. Nataf, Evidence for a high-energy tail in the gamma-ray spectra of globular clusters, *Mon. Not. Roy. Astron. Soc.* **507**, 5161 (2021), [arXiv:2102.00061 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [52] M. Amenomori *et al.* (Tibet AS $_{\gamma}$ Collaboration), First detection of sub-pev diffuse gamma rays from the galactic disk:

- Evidence for ubiquitous galactic cosmic rays beyond peV energies, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **126**, 141101 (2021).
- [53] Z. Cao *et al.* (LHAASO), The First LHAASO Catalog of Gamma-Ray Sources, (2023), [arXiv:2305.17030 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [54] K. Yan and R.-Y. Liu, Constraints on the e^\pm Pair Injection of Pulsar Halos: Implications from the Galactic Diffuse Multi-TeV Gamma-ray Emission, *Phys. Rev. D* **107**, 103028 (2023), [arXiv:2304.12574 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [55] V. Vecchiotti, F. Zuccarini, F. L. Villante, and G. Pagliaroli, Unresolved Sources Naturally Contribute to PeV Gamma-Ray Diffuse Emission Observed by Tibet AS γ , *Astrophys. J.* **928**, 19 (2022), [arXiv:2107.14584 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [56] V. Vecchiotti, G. Pagliaroli, and F. L. Villante, The contribution of Galactic TeV pulsar wind nebulae to Fermi-LAT diffuse emission [10.1038/s42005-022-00939-7](#) (2021), [arXiv:2107.03236 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [57] T. Linden and B. J. Buckman, Pulsar TeV Halos Explain the Diffuse TeV Excess Observed by Milagro, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120**, 121101 (2018), [arXiv:1707.01905 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [58] R.-Y. Liu and X.-Y. Wang, Origin of galactic sub-pev diffuse gamma-ray emission: Constraints from high-energy neutrino observations, *The Astrophysical Journal Letters* **914**, L7 (2021).
- [59] S. M. Osipov, A. M. Bykov, A. E. Petrov, and V. I. Romansky, Energetic positron propagation from pulsars: an analytical two-zone diffusion model, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* **1697**, 012009 (2020).
- [60] C. Evoli, T. Linden, and G. Morlino, Self-generated cosmic-ray confinement in TeV halos: Implications for TeV γ -ray emission and the positron excess, *Phys. Rev. D* **98**, 063017 (2018), [arXiv:1807.09263 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [61] P. Mukhopadhyay and T. Linden, Self-generated cosmic-ray turbulence can explain the morphology of TeV halos, *Phys. Rev. D* **105**, 123008 (2022), [arXiv:2111.01143 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [62] L.-Z. Bao, K. Fang, X.-J. Bi, and S.-H. Wang, Slow Diffusion is Necessary to Explain the γ -Ray Pulsar Halos, *Astrophys. J.* **936**, 183 (2022), [arXiv:2107.07395 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#).
- [63] A. U. Abeysekara *et al.* (HAWC), Multiple Galactic Sources with Emission Above 56 TeV Detected by HAWC, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **124**, 021102 (2020), [arXiv:1909.08609 \[astro-ph.HE\]](#)